

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol-1, Number 2, September- 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10213429

KNOWLEDGE, KNOW HOW TO TEACH: REFLECTIONS FOR A DECOLONIAL EDUCATION IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

AUTHOR

Larysa Santos Pinto: Graduated in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Elementary School Teacher at Vira-Virou school.

FEMALE VOICES

Conceição Evaristo

My great-grandmother's voice
echoed as a child in the holds of the ship. It echoed the wails of a lost childhood.

My grandmother's voice
echoed obedience to the whites who own everything.

My mother's voice
echoed in a rebellious whisper in the back of other people's kitchens, under the bundles of dirty clothes worn by white people along the dusty road to the favela.

My voice still
echoes perplexing verses with rhymes of blood and hunger.

My daughter's voice collects all our voices collects in her mute silent voices choked in her throat. My daughter's voice collects in her speech and action. Yesterday – today – now. -freedom.

TEACHER

Before starting work on the experiences of the Pre 1 group, I would like to make a brief account of my journey to this space and my process of building racial literacy.

I graduated in pedagogy from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. During my training, I participated in the study and research group on Anti-Racist Education (GEPEAR/UFRJ) and this period was more than a deepening in the search for racial awareness to promote a decolonial education, it was also a time of discovery, of self-reflection and bringing to light pains not even revealed yet.

Since I was a little girl, I was reminded, almost daily, by my mother, that I had one foot in the slave quarters, I realized that there was much more than one member in this place of suffering. Throughout my research and debates, I had tears unveiled when I made unpalatable discoveries, sleepless nights after realizing the lack of information about my origin and 'starts' that past episodes were not "accidentally" or "coincidences", and so, in addition to expanding reflections, I became aware of the impacts of racism in the school space, both in acts committed by children, often in a joking tone, and in acts committed by people who should be committed to annihilating this type of practice.

Silvio de Almeida, author of the book *Structural Racism* (2019) says that:

"Institutions are just the materialization of a social structure or a mode of socialization that has racism as one of its organic components. Put more bluntly: institutions are racist because society is racist."

After this awakening, I started to pay attention to the proposed projects, characters, and professional references brought to be presented to the children. For most of my training period, I was in small children's classrooms and this made my thinking conditioned to the reception of early childhood education. With this, some questions arise:

- How to bring such delicate topics to the conversation circles?

- How to promote dialogue without bringing guilt

and causing mental confusion to white children?

- How to propose an anti-racist walk from early childhood education?

These doubts are always with me and keep me researching and reflecting on the most appropriate way to approach and bring such a sensitive and important topic to children, to continue promoting egalitarian education.

In the search for an anti-racist and more critical practice on various topics, I began to desire a workspace that would allow for such reflections and that would promote debates on the need to break with practices rooted in our history. Along the way, I found *Vira-virus*, which is a school that enables continuous debates about our daily work and places itself as a space that values different cultures, consequently enabling the broadening of the eyes of both teachers and students and those responsible for influences in the construction of Brazilian culture, which means valuing the culture of native peoples, standing out in this context, indigenous and African.

After my journey, I begin my journey with the Pre 1 group from here, recalling an excerpt from the opinion of Law 10.639/03 on the importance of pedagogies that value the history and contribution of black people to the development of Brazilian culture:

"Pedagogies to combat racism and discrimination designed to educate positive ethnic/racial relations aim to strengthen black consciousness among blacks and awaken black consciousness among whites. Among blacks, they will be able to offer knowledge and security to be proud of their African origin; for whites, it may allow them to identify the influences, contribution, participation, and importance of black history and culture in their way of being, living, relating to other people, notably black people. They will also be part of a process of recognition, by the State, society, and the school, of the social debt they owe to the black segment of the population, enabling an explicit position to be taken against racism and racial discrimination

and the construction of affirmative actions in the different teaching levels of Brazilian education.” (GONÇALVES E SILVA, 2004, p.10).

BEFORE THE START

This work is not about exposing a project developed in the Pre 1 class, but rather a reflection on the need for and importance of an attentive and conscious teaching practice, which I sought to explore in this year of 2022 with the group.

Throughout the year I tried to remain vigilant so that the moments of planning the proposals did not fail to contain a reflection on how to include significant references and could contemplate and value Afro culture. Believing that we should not wait for a theme or a “commemorative” date to appear to work on the history and contribution of African peoples in the construction of our culture, I reiterate that the process is continuous and continues to be present in the routine of the Pre 1 whenever I post the possibility of insertion.

Part of the first experiences with racism occurs at school and in early childhood education. It is essential to recognize that children see differences and can verbalize them. When we observe comparative comments about bodies, hair, skin, and other characteristics, such as phenotypic, children are making it clear that they realize that we are not all the same, as some people say, and end up silencing debates that could contribute to the deconstruction of racist practices. Therefore, we teachers need to make it clear that there is no problem with plurality, whatever the sphere, quite the contrary. By bringing heterogeneity as enriching, we strengthen black and white children. We tend to think that race is just about black people, as if “white” isn’t race either. Dialogue about racism is indispensable as it impacts the development of identity construction, as reflected by philosopher Djamila.

“ In a society like the Brazilian one, with a slavery heritage, black people will experience racism from the place of those who are the object of this oppression, from the place that restricts opportunities because of this system of oppression. So

both groups can and should discuss these issues, but they will speak from different places.” (Ribeiro, 2017, p. 86)

People are not born racist, but with the reproduction of certain patterns throughout life, an “anti-black” movement spreads, a look where everything that belongs to whites is validated and what comes from blacks is inferior. And so, black people are weakening and looking for alternatives to be accepted in a society that is exempt from the problem daily.

A white child grows and develops surrounded by references that help build self-esteem. On TV, in literature, in toys that fill store shelves, and in cartoons. There is a very thick layer of representations that place the image of white people as a standard, correct, beautiful figure, and for the irreprehensible to exist, there must be a lack of form. We then find black children growing up with numerous gaps in this process of building a framework, since it is not possible to come across figures that help them to represent the projections of their dreams.

Although we walk in a crescent, it is not the rule to find characters valued by childhood with dark skin, curly hair, and well-marked features and this creates a distance between black bodies and their ancestry, causing a conflicting relationship with their blackness. In an interview for the national early childhood network, Ana Oliva, a psychologist and master in education and social justice, talks about the importance of representativeness in childhood:

“ Childhood, especially early childhood (0 to 6 years old) is central to the subject’s development. It is in early childhood that the child builds the basic skills of a human being (walking, talking, symbolizing). It is also a stage of building bonds, identity, and self-esteem. It is in this phase that the subject will build his bases for the relationship with himself and with others. Therefore, diversity, representativeness, identity, and culture are central discussions for the promotion of rights and the construction of subjectivity in childhood .”

Along my trajectory, between internships and conducting, I was able to be inside some middle-class schools in the city of Rio and the truth is that it is not common to find black students in these spaces, since the black population finds it very difficult to achieve such status. My arrival at Vira-Virou was full of pleasant surprises. Unfortunately, it is still not possible for us to say that 1/3 of our school's school community is made up of brown or black people, but I still consider it a space where it is possible to see the presence of black children and families more frequently than in other environments and I think that doesn't say enough about our school. I see this coming and going as a portrait of a place heading toward historical deconstruction.

I remember the first days when I arrived at Vira and saw some black students with long, colorful braids. I was surprised, happy, and excited at the same time. I had just arrived at a school that I already admired and saw as a reference in promoting Brazilian popular culture, but I did not expect to find black children so comfortable in an environment where it is notably composed of a white majority. That caught my attention and made me think that in addition to promoting and valuing popular culture, it would also be a possible place to debate racial issues.

Despite already being related to research in favor of anti-racist education, I felt more encouraged to remain in the search for knowledge to further broaden my view and teach feelings and experiences experienced by me, which could contribute to the group. For Maria Lúcia da Silva, a member of the AMMA Psique e Negritude institute, "thinking about the psychic effects of racism is thinking about it as a structuring element of society, but also of the perceptions of affections and the way of thinking about the world". In this sense, I have placed myself as an instrument of transformation, however difficult it may be at times since I suffer daily and direct impacts from this society that I denounce and fight.

This year I had the pleasure of visiting the Museu Afro Brasil, located in Ibirapuera Park in the city of São Paulo. There were so many memories, so much richness and so many discoveries that I went back to school bubbling with desires. After this visit, without a doubt, my speech intensified,

my relationships expanded and my desire to bring different knowledge to children increased.

I started to do more searches for places that could provide me with information to add to my work. I visited the Quilombo Cafundá Astrogilda, which is located in Vargem Grande, very close to our school, I did the African heritage circuit with the Pretos Novos Institute in downtown Rio and since then I have been on the path of research and investigation.

THE YEAR 2022 WITH THE PRE 1 CLASS.

Throughout the school term, it was thought to work on themes such as Afro culture and its contributions to our culture in a very organic way, after all, it is not about canceling white culture and making learning conditional on black knowledge. As previously stated, anti-racist education should not be present only in projects to bring the possibility of debating isolated episodes or on the 20th of November. The construction of a racial conscience takes place daily, especially in a country like Brazil, structurally racist and denialist in this sense, since we recognize the existence of racism, but if questioned about our conventions, most people exempt themselves from attitudes that would be easily questionable. Silvio de Almeida says:

“ Societal change is not only achieved through denunciations or the moral repudiation of racism: it depends, above all, on taking positions and adopting anti-racist practices ” (2019, p. 52)

Considering this thought, the experiences thought and proposed for the group were permeated by figures, symbols, and materialities that could contribute to the fight against racism and its impacts in the school context without requiring dense or delicate conversations for the group that has children between 4 and 5 years. The materials

brought were offered lightly, but without forgetting to talk about their origins and their contributions to society.

Drawing parallels between Brazilian legends and African legends, it was possible to bring to the conversation circles countless similarities between our stories, characters, and scenarios and the group was able to expand its repertoire also through research carried out with the family. Throughout the year we receive contributions of materials that were collected by the family after the child took some report of experience experienced at school. It was common for us to receive photos, texts, poems, drawings made collectively, books, and the like.

Among the many known legends, the Legend of the Baobab caught the attention of children. With interest intensifying, I acquired tools so that we could delve deeper and I took the opportunity to work on territoriality, through observation of the world map and conversations about how far we are from the African continent, it was possible to get to know the book “O Velho Baobá” and think under what conditions these trees arrived in Brazil, we discovered that this tree can also offer us a fruit called ‘MUKUA’ which is commonly used in culinary dishes to add vitamins and minerals to meals. On a visit to Porto de Galinhas, student Helena Paciello registered Baobá at the hotel where she stayed. Those responsible sent us the photos through the class app to share with the class. It was a joy to realize the presence of Baobabs in our country.

All these subjects were derived from a single legend and it was not necessary to bring a story of suffering and subalternity, as is common in the presentation of black history. As John Henrik Clarke would say, “If you start your story in slavery, everything after that will feel like progress.” And we still have a lot to progress, so it’s important to bring the potential and fight in the history of this people.

With the partnership of area professors, it was possible to expand the conversations to different fields and thus explore different formats. Professor Vinícius greatly contributed to our journey, both in activities with the children and in the exchange of ideas, where I was able to learn about different narratives on multiple topics. In an exchange with the team, it is possible to enrich and think about possible ways to contemplate the countless archetypes of our society.

To encourage and contribute to the formation

of citizens who understand cultural plurality and deal positively with differences, it is necessary to deconstruct a curriculum that is still presented in a historically Eurocentric format. In the development of a decolonial work, it is important to recognize the existing political implications in the documents that are made available for the maintenance of territories of power, to then trace shortcuts to an education that frees us from historical ties. Antônio Flávio Moreira and Tomaz Tadeu da Silva say:

“ The curriculum is not an innocent and neutral element of disinterested transmission of social knowledge. The curriculum is implicated in power relations, the curriculum conveys particular and interesting social views, and the curriculum produces particular individual and social identities. The curriculum is not a transcendent and timeless element – it has a history, linked to specific and contingent forms of organization of society and education ”.

Knowing this, we started to fight for a change not only in the curriculum, but in the postures adopted in our daily lives and, mainly, in our practice. Literature is a great ally. In addition to encouraging the habit of reading, contributing to the development of creativity, and providing emotional, social, and cognitive development, it is possible to bring “common” stories, which do not necessarily deal with a militancy theme, but which have dark-skinned characters, something that is not customary in toys for children and this means that more and more black children find representation and identification and white children can also perceive black people in places of protagonism.

One of the first stories I took to the group was ‘Little Red Riding Hood and the Pink Boto, from a collection of re-signified classic tales by Mazza. This story takes place on the banks of the Negro River, in the Amazon, the girl lives with her mother in a village of floating houses and while taking a basket of tacacá and fruits from the region to her sick grandmother, she talks to a pink river dolphin and gets distracted by the beauties of the forest. The little red riding hood with black fur on the cover caught my attention right away. Some even questioned that that couldn’t be the story of Little Riding Hood because “Little Riding Hood is not like

that” - it was the speech of a child. We then started a conversation about what the story of Chapeuzinho was about and what would be essential for us to classify the story and recognize the character. Throughout the conversation, we were building the understanding that there are no physical characteristics that put characters in their places. Characters belong to imagination and possibilities. Each narrative is composed of an idealization and even though in our imagination and some descriptions, princesses, princes, and prominent characters appear as European stereotypes, there is not just one perspective, as we are made up of many peoples.

In every collection of Mazza’s resignified short stories, the characters are black and racial issues are not raised, but bring characteristics of our regionality, give Brazilianness to the narrative, bring our fauna, flora, and legends as an integral part of our culture and thus it was possible to address themes relevant and contributors in the perspective of breaking a Eurocentric narrative and disconnected from reality. In Rodriguez’s words:

“... reading is one of the ways children understand and interpret the world, bringing cultural and social enrichment, contributing to cognitive and psychological development, in addition to language appropriation.”

In addition to relying on the help of literature as a tool, we organically included black figures in our daily lives through the proposals in the handouts, the forms made in our routine and some, intentionally, went on weekends to be done with the families. Gradually, figures from different cultural backgrounds were introduced into our praxis and the group’s imagination, causing us to no longer have reactions of estrangement, but of awakening curiosity.

The group experienced contact with black culture in different ways. We know jokes, legends, cuisines, and geography. Even our project 'Mundo dos Dinossauros', from the second half of the year, traveled across the African continent, paralleling our folklore. During our research on Brazilian dinosaurs, we met a dinosaur called Sacisaurus. With this name and its bony characteristics, there was no way we could not return to legends and jokes.

With the book 'Kakokopi, Kakopi! Playing and playing with children from twenty African countries, we got to know many fun games from different regions and one of them became the most beloved in Pre 1, Sasakuru. The game consists of joining friends back to back and arm in arm and trying to reach the finish line balancing on one leg. Evaluating the characteristics of the group and taking into account issues of body maturation, we did not try to run with just one leg, but the challenge of arm-in-arm, back, and orderly walking was great fun. We play many times and the class often asks to play again. The video below illustrates one of these experiences:

CONCLUSION

This work aimed to share the daily anguish of teachers who seek to break with slavery currents by promoting an anti-racist education within a school environment, specifically with young children, where it becomes more sensitive and delicate to deal with issues like this.

Sharing the path traveled with the pre-1 class during this year of 2022 is a way of making available to my colleagues the possibilities thought of during that period, but with the attention of other committed teachers and a joint reflection can be transformed and improved. to remain in search of the annihilation of unfair and inhumane practices that affect the dignity of human beings.

I believe that the professionals who were formed after the enactment of Law 10.639/03, whether in the area of pedagogy or in any other course that has the option of doing a degree, should have in their curricula, if not full, enough foundation for them that they should promote in classrooms, after all, the law contemplates interdisciplinarity, it is not limited to history classes.

We walk at a slow pace, but little by little it is possible to witness changes. When a 5-year-old child, while making a self-portrait drawing, clarifies to his friends that there is no such thing as “skin color” because each skin has a tone and, therefore, there are different skin colors and a pencil color cannot be an only one representative, we noticed that the new generation develops more alert and attentive. It is in this direction that I want to go and will continue to provide myself with information to be able to supply whatever is of interest to these small citizens who are already interested in transforming their futures. I recall here a famous line by Angela Davis, an American philosopher activist: “It is not enough not to be racist, you must be anti-racist”.

I became a teacher because I believe in education as the greatest tool for transformation and although it is not an easy profession, it is perhaps the most rewarding in the world. We see the result of our work bloom daily, little by little until it becomes big and potent. I wish to be able to witness this group fill up with arguments and strength to contribute to a struggle that does not belong only to black people. Even though the majority of children in our school are fair-skinned people, we must work together so that we can count on white people as allies. Unfortunately, it is still necessary to think strategically about the paths outlined and my practice is always in motion, alert, and always contributing.

“If education alone does not transform society, without it society does not change either.” Paulo Freire

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